

A Comparative Study on Physical Progress in Kerala under Mahathma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme (NREGS)

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ABSTRACT

NREG Act is an important step towards the realization of the right to work. NREGS scheme also expected to enhance people's livelihoods on a sustained basis, by developing the economic and social infrastructure in rural areas. The Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act, 2005 (MGNREGA) guarantees 100 days of employment in a financial year to any rural household whose adult members are willing to do unskilled manual work. Here the researcher focus to study physical progress in Kerala under NREG scheme from 2014-15 to 2018-19.

KEYWORD: NREG scheme, physical progress, person days generated.

I. INTRODUCTION

A majority of the poor in rural areas of the country depend mainly on the wages they earn through unskilled, casual, manual labour. They are often on threshold levels of subsistence, and are vulnerable to the possibility of sinking from transient to chronic poverty. Inadequate labour demand or unpredictable crises that may be general in nature, like natural disaster or personal like ill-health, all adversely impact their employment opportunities. In a context of poverty & unemployment, workfare programmes have been important interventions in developed as well as developing countries for many years. These programmes typically provide unskilled manual workers with short-term employment on public works such as, irrigation infrastructure, reforestation, soil conservation and road construction. The rationale for workfare programmes rests on some. The

programmes provide income transfers to poor households during critical times and also enable consumption smoothing, especially during slack agricultural seasons or years. In countries with high unemployment rates, transfer benefits from workfare programmes can prevent poverty from worsening, particularly during lean periods. Durable assets that these programmes may create have the potential to generate second-round employment benefits as needed infrastructure is developed.

NREGA

The National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (NREGA) aims at enhancing the livelihood security of the people in rural areas by guaranteeing hundred days of wage employment in a financial year, to a rural household whose members volunteer to do unskilled manual work. The objective of the Act is create durable assets and strengthen the livelihood resource base of the rural poor. The choice of works suggested in the Act address causes of chronic poverty like drought, deforestation, soil erosion, so that the process of employment generation is on a sustainable basis works suggested in the Act addresses causes of chronic poverty like drought, deforestation and soil erosion, so that the process of employment generation is maintained on a sustainable basis.

MGNREGA in Kerala: To tackle the problem of unemployment, under employment and poverty among the rural population in Karnataka, MGNREGA has been introduced on 2006- 2007. Wayanad and Palakkad are the two backward districts identified in

phase I. Then it universalized by covering all districts In Kerala. Now MGNREGA focus to ensure livelihood and food security to the rural poor through creating sustainable assets.

II. Statement of the problem.

Physical progress is the progress the project makes with respect to time, resource or durations. The study aims a comparative Analysis of physical progress in Kerala in the last two years under NREGA scheme .

2.1 Methodology: The study is based on secondary source of data such as books, records, Government documents, journals, magazines and official records of Ministry of Rural Development and Panchayat Raj, Government of Kerala and Government of India, websites.

2.2 Area of the Study: The study was undertaken in Kerala:

2.3 Tools for Analysis: statistical tools such as comparative statement sand percentages are used to derive valid conclusions from the study.

2.4 Objectives of the study.

The primary objective of the study to understand physical progress in Kerala in the last few years .Primary objective is fulfilled by attaining the secondary objectives.

- To know about Employment Provided to Disabled Persons in Kerala in the last two years.
- To make a Comparative analysis of Employment Provided Period wise.
- To understand Employment Patterns During the last years.
- To know about SC ST Employment Status in Kerala.

3.1 TREND ANALYSIS OF PHYSICAL PROGRESS OF KERALA IN LAST 4 YEARS

DATA

TREND

II Physical Progress	FY 2017-2018	FY 2016-2017	FY 2015-2016	FY 2014-2015	2014-2015	2015-2016	2016-2017	2017-2018
Approved Labour Budget[In Lakhs]	450	603.11	713	761.4	100	93.6	79.2	59.1
Person days Generated so far[In Lakhs]	619.59	684.62	741.74	588.72	100	126.0	116.3	105.2
% of Total LB	137.69	113.52	104.03	77.32	100	134.5	146.8	178.1
SC person days % as of total person days	16.25	17	17.4	17.48	100	99.5	97.3	93.0
ST person days % as of total person days	4.56	4.47	3.93	3.88	100	101.3	115.2	117.5
Women Person days out of Total (%)	90.76	91.08	91.27	92.16	100	99.0	98.8	98.5
Average days of employment provided per Household	47.24	46.97	49.26	42.65	100	115.5	110.1	110.8
Average Wage rate per day per person(Rs.)	260.91	243.09	231.82	214.28	100	108.2	113.4	121.8
Total No of HHs completed 100 Days of Wage Employment	1,17,370	1,13,187	1,65,988	98,648	100	168.0	114.7	119.0
Total Households Worked[In Lakhs]	13.12	14.57	15.06	13.8	100	109.1	105.6	95.1
Total Individuals Worked[In Lakhs]	14.71	16.44	16.93	15.13	100	111.9	108.7	97.2
Differently abled persons worked	1740	2005	1981	1753	100	113.0	114.0	88.5

Source: www.mgnrega.nic.in

During the last financial year 2017-18, 47.24 lakh average days of employments have been provided to households and 619.59.lakh person days of employment generated. The program has attracted down trodden groups like Scheduled Caste (16.25%), Scheduled Tribes (4.56%) and women (90.76%) while comparing with the base year (2014-2015) the statistics shows a decreasing trend on physical progress in Kerala.

3.2 Works completed during the period from 2006-07 to 2014-

Year	Total No. of Works Taken up (New + Spill Over)[In Lakhs]	Number of Ongoing Works[In Lakhs]	Number of Completed Works
2018-19	2.08	1.87	21,327
2017-18	2.93	1.65	1,27,474
2016-2017	3.65	1	2,64,299
2015-2016	3.53	1.51	2,01,276
2014-2015	2.96	1.1	1,86,056
Total	15.15	7.13	8

Source: www.mgnrega.nic.in

Table-3.2 shows that out of the total 15lakhs works taken up, only 8lakhs works have been completed and 7.13lakhs works are still in progress from 2014-15 to 2018-19. The performance in terms of completed work is quite low.

3.3 Employment provided to different categories

YEAR	SC person days % as of total person days	ST person days % as of total person days	Women Person days out of Total (%)
2018-19	16.77	6.33	90.14
2017-18	16.25	4.56	90.76
2016-2017	17	4.47	91.08
2015-2016	17.4	3.93	91.27
2014-2015	17.48	3.88	92.16

Source: www.mgnrega.nic.in

Table-3.3 shows the employment provided to different categories from 2014-15 to 2018-19 in Kerala. From the table it is clear that there is a drastic increase in the involvement of ST workers in NREG scheme every year. The study also reveals that majority of NREG workers are women.

3.4 person days generated

YEAR	Person days Generated so far[In Lakhs]	SC person days % as of total person days	ST person days % as of total person days	Women Person days out of Total (%)	Total No of HHs completed 100 Days of Wage Employment
2019-18	216.32	16.77	6.33	90.14	842
2018-17	619.59	16.25	4.56	90.76	1,17,370
2017-2016	684.62	17	4.47	91.08	1,13,187
2016-2015	741.74	17.4	3.93	91.27	1,65,988
2015-2014	588.72	17.48	3.88	92.16	98,648

Source: www.mgnrega.nic.in

Table-3.4 shows the details of person days generated from 2014-2015-2018-19. In total person days of 28.50 .crores, the share of SC category is 16.98% ST category is 4.64%.. During the year 2015-16 total person days generated was 741.74Lakhs and it has

decreased to 619.59Lakhs person days in 2017-18. During the year 2014-15 total No of HHs completed 100 Days of Wage Employment was 98648 and it has increased only to 1,17,370 in 2017-18.

Summary

Since the inception of MGNREGA it has generated 28.5 crore person days from 2014-2015 onwards. The present average wage earned is Rs.273.93/- per day as it was Rs.214.28/- per day in 2014-2015. It shows that the average wage has been substantially increased in the state but it is not enough to cope up with inflation and standard of living. The state has provided employment to 66.8 lakhs rural households and 74 lakhs individuals under MGNREGA. Out of which the share of the marginalized groups like of SC category is 16.98% and ST category is 4.64%.

Conclusion

MGNREGA is the largest employment providing program in India. It has provided work to 11.28 crore rural workers in India. It addressed 41% of the problem of under employment in rural areas. From 2014-2015 onwards 28.5 days of employment has been generated in Kerala. MGNREGA has helped in

improving the occupation in rustic regions by giving 100 days of ensured wage work in each budgetary year to every household who volunteers to do unskilled manual work. It likewise helped in the making of sturdy resources that can give ecological administrations and economical occupation; decrease in trouble rustic movement and work cooperation by women, SC, ST and crippled people. MGNREGA helps in reinforcing of gross root process of democracy

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